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Research Article

**THE SIGNIFICANCE OF DENTAL SCANNING IN THE
PROGRESSION OF THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SINUSES
OF MIXILLA & ADJOINING STRUCTURE**¹Dr. Sana Khalid, ²Dr Rumesa Nasir, ³Dr. Maida Khan¹Combined Military Hospital Sialkot²Rawalpindi Medical College³Mayo Hospital Lahore**Abstract:**

Objectives: The main objective of this research work was to interrogate the significance of the dental scanning in the search of the association among the space of maxillary subsequent roots of teeth & the floor of the sinus with the utilization of Dental scan.

Duration: This research work started in April 2017 and lasted up to September 2017 at Punjab Dental Hospital, Lahore.

Methodology: The images of Dental scan of 60 patients from 1st premolar of maxilla to the 2nd molar of maxilla. There are 4 types of Dental scan to know the relationship of the root of tooth with the sinus of maxilla. The measurement of the space between the floor of sinus & root of sinus, the thickness of the bone between cortical plate of alveolar & root carried out for analysis.

Conclusion: The thickness of the bone was not thick in the premolar of maxilla & maxillary molar in relation with the other maxillary subsequent roots of teeth. Anatomical association enhanced the awareness & led us to future treatment of suitable planning before surgery. This can be helpful in the prevention of the problems faced at the time of surgical methods.

Key words: Sinus, anatomical, surgery, maxilla, scan, alveolar.

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INTRODUCTION:

The anatomical association is very vital in the choice of the treatment. We can use a method of treatment effectively if we know the association [1]. Sinus of maxilla starts in the age of infancy. The Appearance & extent of this disease alters with the enhancement of the age [2]. It is observable on X-ray that roots enter into the floor of sinus but it is sinus of maxilla that has increases around the teeth roots. Removal of tooth has the ability to create perforation & formation of the oroantral fistula or displacement of the root into the sinus of maxilla if it is very near to the sinus of maxilla [3].

The anatomical association is very important in deciding the movements of the orthodontic tooth. Sinus can initiate on floor or increase of infection from the region of periapical to the region of the sinus [4]. The bone thickness between the cortical plate of alveolar & roots of the molar of maxilla placed a large impact on the increase of the odontogenic infection [5]. The aim of this research work is to enquire maxillary subsequent teeth to sinus of maxilla & to calculate the distance of root of posterior tooth of maxilla and floor of sinus & to find out the bone thickness among the tooth root & cortical plate of alveolar with the utilization of Dental scan .

METHODOLOGY:

This is a retrograde work based upon sampling with the calculations performed by Dental scan of 60 patients. Dental scan is a software which provides CT imaging of the maxilla and mandible in 3 reference planes. The Dental scan has proved itself as the detection method to suppose the attack in the mandible in those sufferers who are the patients of carcinoma of oral squamous.

Dental scan images collected from all the patients from maxillary premolar to molar of the maxilla with removal of the tooth. The collection of the information of all the patients carried out and analysis of this information carried out with the help of SPSS software. The association between the root of tooth & sinus floor is divided into 4 types of images of Dental scan on the basis of the classification of Jung provided in 2009, relationship calculations in type zero & three, the space between root apex of tooth & floor of sinus was calculated in the images of the Denta scan . A + amount is available for apices of root enlarging under the sinus floor & a – amount for the apices of root above the sinus floor.

To calculate the thickness of the bone, the space from roots of subsequent teeth of maxilla to the cortical plate of alveolar can be measured with the help of Dental scan. For the roots of palatal & buccal, the spaces between cortical plates of palatal & buccal calculated respectively. For assessment & comparison of left side & right side calculations, a combine T tests carried out. For measurement of comparison, a paired t-test done. The collected information presented as average, rate & deviation from the standard. To evaluate the thickness of the bone, ANOVA test was in utilization.

RESULTS:

In this research work, Dental scan of 60 patients performed in which twenty six were females & thirty four were male patients. The range of the age of the patients was fourteen to eighteen years. Type zero association was very common in the 1st & 2nd premolars, whereas in the 1st and 2nd maxillary molars, the most common observable type was type one as shown in Table-1.

Table I: Vertical relation of apex root of maxillary posterior teeth and floor of maxillary sinus					
Tooth		Type 0, n (%)	Type 1, n (%)	Type 2, n (%)	Type 3, n (%)
Maxillary first premolar	B	48.00 (96.0)	2.00 (4.0)	-	-
	P	48.00 (5.0)	2.00 (5.0)	-	-
Maxillary second premolar	B	35.00 (70.0)	14.00 (28.0)	-	1.00 (2.0)
	P	32.00 (65.0)	17.00 (34.0)		1.00 (1.0)
Maxillary first molar	MB	15.00 (30.0)	28.00 (57.0)	2.00 (4.0)	4.00 (9.0)
	DB	18.00 (36.0)	22.00 (45.0)	8.00 (17.0)	1.00 (2.0)
	P	21.00 (41.0)	21.00 (42.0)	7.00 (15.0)	1.00 (2.0)
Maxillary second molar	MB	14.00 (28.0)	30.00 (61.0)	-	6.00 (11.0)
	DB	28.00 (57.0)	21.00 (42.0)	1.00 (1.0)	-
	P	33.00 (66.0)	16.00 (32.0)	1.00 (1.0)	1.00 (1.0)

The average distance from maxilla floor to the tooth root was largest for molar’s palatal root & premolar’s buccal root. Distance was smallest for the root of mesiobuccal of maxillary 1st & palatal 2nd premolar root as described in Table-2.

Table II: Mean distance from the maxillary posterior teeth to respective cortical plate in mm

Maxillary 1st Premolar	B	0.80
	P	1.40
Maxillary second premolar	B	1.60
	P	1.70
Maxillary first molar	MB	1.00
	DB	1.90
	P	1.20
Maxillary second molar	MB	2.20
	DB	2.50
	P	1.80

The space between the association of the sinus of maxilla & root of the teeth for right to the left was not analytically purposeful; the association between various types was available as significant statistically. The root of the buccal root of 1st premolar of maxilla & root of mesiobuccal of 1st molar of maxilla were available very near to the cortical plate. The root of the distobuccal of 3rd molar of maxilla observed very far from that plate. Between the 4 vertical associations, a statistically important disparity was available in the thickness of the bone adjacent to the roots.

DISCUSSION:

It was very hard to evaluate the association between maxillary subsequent root of the tooth & sinus floor before the initiation of any method for treatment to prevent the complications of the procedures. There are some dangers which are linked with subsequent root tips of maxilla very near to the floor of sinus i.e. during the method of endodontic, there is high danger of hole in the floor of sinus with the instrument of root canal in type one & type three associations. The patient of orbital abscess was also present in this subject; this may be the outcome from a hasty action that initiates disease of swelling of periapical after procedure of the endodontic for the molar of maxilla. It is justified reality that at the time of periapical operation, radiographs of the traditional periapical should not be utilized in the supposition of the maxillary sinus damage.

The modalities of the advance imaging as dental scan

or CBCT (cone beam CT) are very effective [6]. The analysis of cone beam CT has the ability to show the important association between thickness of the mucosa of sinus & periodontal abnormality. Bacteria & viruses are the reasons of many infections. So, it is decided that a pure association is present between lesions of periodontal & thickness of maxillary mucosa of sinus [7, 8]. Huang & Brunsvold reported a patient of sinusitis of maxilla from procedure periodontal treatment of 1st molar found with abnormality of bone [9, 10]. Eberhardt concluded that roots of mesiobuccal 2nd molar of maxilla were available very near to the sinus floor. Kilic found that the root of distobuccal of 2nd molar of maxilla was very close to the floor of sinus [11, 12].

Jung and Cho in their case study carried out by the utilization of cone beam CT images for molars concluded that the root of buccal very frequently enters into the sinus of maxilla. The outcome of this research work showed that the roots of mesiobuccal of 1st molar of maxilla were observable very close to the floor of sinus. Arijji in his research work concluded that molars of maxilla the root of the buccal observed very close to the cortical plate of the buccal [13]. The outcome of this research work showed that the bone thickness was very less for the roots of mesiobuccal of maxillary 1st molar & largest for the roots of distobuccal of molar of maxilla.

CONCLUSION:

A very vital association observed among the maxillary subsequent teeth & sinus floor with the

roots of buccal & palate. The root of buccal of molars was present embedded into the MS (maxillary sinus). The bone thickness was very small in the maxillary premolar & maxillary molar in relation to other roots of the posterior teeth of maxilla. Aforementioned awareness of the anatomical association among MPT (maxillary posterior tooth) & maxillary sinus leads us to acknowledge the association in suitable planning of the treatment before surgery. It also gives us the guiding principles to prevent the problems faced during the performance of the minor oral operational methods which are very frequent in the methods of dentistry.

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